

8T – Odd Photon Absorptions and The Graviton

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Abstract:

By analyzing the numerical term of the photon and the electron given by the primordial coupling series it is possible to ensure that there can not be partial absorption of a photon onto the Electron. That is because when summed they form an even number, which has to vanish from the manifold onto the electron. The framework indicate that the electron can absorb or emit only odd amount of Bosons together, that insight leading us to a Graviton particle composed by three photons.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the matrix tensor M, given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other matrix tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equations (1.2) and (1.1). By (1.2) those manifolds are topologically invariant. Flatness is an immediate result of this framework as given by the illustration below.

$$\frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\sum_{m=1}^K \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_m} \frac{\partial s_m}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=1}^K \frac{\partial \ell}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2.A)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matrix tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30: 128: 850: 9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \tag{1.43}$$

For example, the Electromagnetic coupling term, we have proven the invariant three to be an electron by putting it in the fine structure constant formula:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

We have described the arbitrary variations of the manifold by the term on the main equation:

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} \delta g - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} \delta g' = 0 \quad (1.46)$$

We partitioned and discretized the arbitrary variation term and derived the existence of Fermion. In particular, we have shown that it must have an even amount of elements, which differ in sign and create nine threefold combination, and no more than two distinct elements.

$$\delta g_1 + \delta g_2 \dots = \sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i \quad (1.47)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N \delta g_i = 0 \quad (1.48)$$

In addition, with bosons, described by the term (1.49) as they were proven discrete amount of prime curvature on the matric tensor:

$$\sum_{i=1}^M \delta g_i > 0 \quad (1.49)$$

We have presented the spin classification in the 8T thesis, page seventeen, while using the prime critical line:

Spin 0: $2N_0$ variations

Spin $\frac{1}{2}$: $2N_0 + 3$ variations

Spin 1: $2N_0 + 3 + N_V$ variations

Spin $N = 2N_0 + 3 + N_{V1} + N_{V2} \dots$ variations

Let us analyze the second coupling term in the primorial (1.41):

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma$$

Suppose that the photon now getting onto the electron, since the electron has no definite location but rather itself is a cloud of probability, the chances of a photon to get scattered onto the electron as a particle are rather small. However taking into account the prime number feature and the propagation all across the matric in all directions, the photon will get scattered onto the electron. When they do, we can represent the coupling term:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \bar{\gamma}$$

Since the photon is prime and so does the electron, they sum up to an even number as one previously covered in the thesis. Theorem (2) the photon is a net curvature of prime discrete amount, and the electron was proven the invariant three.

$$[(e)] + \tilde{\gamma} = 3 + 5$$

As reader probably knows by now that even amount of variations are correlated to zero, that is how we derived the existence of fermions, and how we derived the invariant three to be an Electron.

$$[(e)] + \gamma = 0$$

That is an indication that there will be a complete absorption of the photon onto the electron. We have introduced the superscript on the electron to sum the elements it contains.

$$e \rightarrow e^{\mathcal{K}}$$

$$\mathcal{K} \in \mathbb{R}$$

For the electron that absorbed a photon, the new parameterization will be:

$$e^{\mathcal{K}} = e^{+1}$$

For the electron that emitted the photon the probability in the new parameterization will be:

$$e^{\mathcal{K}} = e^0$$

We need to introduce a sub-script to differentiate the two electrons, so overall:

$$e^{\mathcal{K}} = e^{+1} \rightarrow e_1^{+1}$$

$$e^{\mathcal{K}} = e^0 \rightarrow e_0^0$$

Suppose the electron that absorbed now absorbed an additional two photons at the same time:

$$[(e)] + \tilde{\gamma} + \tilde{\gamma} = 3 + 5 + 5$$

They don't sum to an even number, which indicate that the absorption of a photon cluster by a single electron could not exceed one photon at the time. Alternatively that the photon can **absorb only odd number of photons together**:

$$[(e)] + \tilde{\gamma} + \tilde{\gamma} + \tilde{\gamma} = 3 + 5 + 5 + 5 = 0$$

Notice that if the absorption of three net variations is possible and complete, so does the emission of three net variations, now for the Electric coupling term assume instead of absorption we would have an emission.

$$[(e)] + \vec{\gamma} + \vec{\gamma} + \vec{\gamma}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (e)] + \vec{\gamma} + \vec{\gamma} + \vec{\gamma}$$

Which is exactly the structure of the Graviton, as in the 8T thesis we considered it to be the combination of three net variations, summing up to spin two.

$$[(24 * 5) + (e)] + \vec{\gamma} + \vec{\gamma} + \vec{\gamma} = 2N_2 + 2$$

If we can create a situation in which an electron will be emitting three photons at the same moment, than the result would be a Spin two particle, i.e. a Graviton which is composed of three photons. However in order for the Electron to emit three photons it has to absorb three photons and retain them, the photons emission must be in sync to reach the desired higher spin to which we correlate the Graviton. The creation of the Graviton than is decreasing as time goes by as one theorized that the electron aspiring lowest index in the superscript over time, synonymous with the lowest state of energy, (subscript meant to index the electron itself, to classify which one absorbed and which one emitted).

$$e_N^{\mathcal{K}} \rightarrow e_N^0$$

For some time parameter:

$$t \rightarrow \infty$$

That is to state that leptons has a varying probability of emission over time, and if we aspire to be more brave, according to the superscript prediction, the probability of **emission** should be lower, and aspire zero over time.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)

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